

THE CONCEPT OF SOCIAL MEDIA, ITS MEANS, ROLE, TYPES A AND CHARACTERISTICS

مفهوم الإعلام الاجتماعي ووسائله و دوره وأنواعه وخصائصه

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مؤخرة. أستاذ قسم علوم القرآن والتفسير كلية العلوم الإسلامية الجامعة الإسلامية العالمية للدراسات الشرعية والإنسانية

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Abstract

During this topic, the concept of social media and its definitions, the reasons for their differences, in addition to its means, types and characteristics will be discussed. This study dealt with the issue of social media in the following elements. The concept of social media its means, tools, types, and characteristics. Issues related to social media today are among the topics worthy of study and care, as the media occupies a large and influential space in various fields of life. Perhaps social media is one of the most prominent types of media in terms of influence and importance, as it is based on transmitting news and information from the community to the community itself, to achieve one of the purposes of news, guidance or guidance through its various means such as clubs, forums, places of worship, social networks, newspapers and books. Whereas social media is of such vitality and importance; This topic has been allocated according to the requirements of the study. Whereas social media is of such vitality and importance; This topic has been allocated according to the requirements of the study. This study was based on the extrapolation of the issues in which the opinions of scholars varied according to the multiplicity of factors related to the edge, according to an applied analytical methodology.

Keywords: concept, social media, means, types, characteristics.

ملخص البحث

خلال هذا المبحث سيتم الوقوف على مفهوم الإعلام الاجتماعي وما ورد فيه من تعريفات، وأسباب اختلافها، إضافة إلى وسائله وأنواعه وخصائصه. تناولت هذه الدراسة موضوع الإعلام الاجتماعي في العناصر التالية:

مفهوم الإعلام الاجتماعي، ووسائله، وأدواته، وأنواعه، وخصائصه. تعد القضايا المتعلقة بالإعلام الاجتماعي في وقتنا الحاضر من الموضوعات الجديرة بالدراسة والعناية، حيث يشغل الإعلام حيزًا كبيرًا ومؤثرًا في مختلف ميادين الحياة. ولعل الإعلام الاجتماعي هو أحد أبرز أنواع الإعلام من جهة التأثير والأهمية، حيث يركز على نقل الأخبار والمعلومات من المجتمع إلى المجتمع نفسه، لتحقيق غرض من الأغراض الإخبارية أو التوجيه أو الإرشاد عبر وسائله المتنوعة كالنوادي والملتقيات ودور العبادة وشبكات التواصل الاجتماعي والصحف والكتب. ويعتبر الإعلام الموجه إلى مكان أو فئة أو شريحة معينة من شرائح المجتمع هو إعلامها الاجتماعي، كالإعلام الموجه لمجتمع مدينة معينة أو شريحة كالنساء، أو فئة كالمعاقين. ولما كان الإعلام الاجتماعي بهذه الحيوية والأهمية؛ خصصت هذا الموضوع وفق ما اقتضته متطلبات الدراسة. ولما كان الإعلام الاجتماعي بهذه الحيوية والأهمية؛ خصصت هذا الموضوع وفق ما اقتضته متطلبات الدراسة. ولقد قامت هذه الدراسة على استقراء المسائل التي تعددت آراء العلماء فيها تبعًا لتعدد العوامل المتعلقة بالحافة وذلك وفق منهجية تطبيقية تحليلية.

الكلمات المفتاحية: مفهوم، الإعلام الاجتماعي، وسائل، أنواع، خصائص.

The first topic: the concept of social media

1 The concept of social media in terms of its vocabulary:

Media is a language: - as previously - its meanings revolve around news, knowledge, education and the transmission of speech from one party to another.

Idiomatically, media: the transmission of information, ideas, opinions, news and behaviors, through physical, visible and moral means of dissemination, with the intent of achieving a purpose.

Social: a name attributed to a meeting, and according to what Ibn Faris says: “The gym, the meem and the eye are one origin that indicates the unity of the thing. It is said: the plural of the thing”.

And in Lisan al-Arab: “The plural of a thing for separation brings it together as a plural. And the total: which is gathered from here and here and here even if it is not made like one thing. And the people gathered: they gathered also from here and here, and the community of al-Baida: most of it and its celebrants, and the people all: gathered, and the assembly.” It is a name for people and for the place in which they gather.

The conclusion from all this is that the meanings of society in the language revolve around: the plural of the dispersed, the inclusion of the dispersed, and the name of the place where people gather.

Society, in the terminology, is: “a self-sufficient social system, sustained by its own forces, and comprising members of both sexes, male and female, of all ages”.

That is, a society is a group of individuals who live according to a specific social system, and are united by common bonds, and characteristics that distinguish them from the rest of the groups. Society: a group of living individuals and not a group of abstract ideas, it has a balance of procedures and means for dealing with the environment, and it is very difficult to set the boundaries of a particular society, as the boundaries are drawn in it according to the purposes, goals, and conditions, and there is nothing to prevent the term (society) from being used) for this or that purpose, it is often used to refer to the totality of social relations, as we say the peasant community, the Bedouin community, the fishermen community, the student community...etc.

Sociology is primarily concerned with the study of society, which is: “a science that studies the emergence, growth, nature, laws and systems of human groups”.

2 .Define Social Media as an Additional Compound:

Researchers have defined social media with many definitions, the most prominent of which are:

1. A term that refers to the various forms of electronic communication that have become possible through the use of computer technologies”.
This definition limits social media to forms of electronic communication, such as social networking sites, forums, blogs, and the like.
2. The media that cares about the news of society and groups and addresses the groups in a collective manner, to introduce the group’s news, whether the society is small or large, and whether it is an organization, an organization or an institution... with the intent of informing and teaching, and with the intent of guiding and influencing collective behavior ”.
It is noted on this definition that it is an explanation of the concept of social media more than it is a definition of it; However, it refers to the concept of social media in general.
3. Media directed to the community, its individuals and groups, with the aim of modifying their behavior, investing their efforts, sharpening their determination, and involving them in development processes, to be useful and productive members, and a natural companion in bringing about the required change ".
This definition deals with social media considering the goals and objectives that it should strive to achieve, but not every social media seeks to achieve such commendable goals, as the media may be corrupt and combative of those goals and objectives to be achieved.
4. Social websites on the Internet... that allow individuals or groups to communicate unlimited and interact with each other through the virtual space.
It is noted on this definition that it deals with social media from a technical perspective, and limits it to the usual social networking sites.
5. Internet Interactive Communication Programs ”.This definition does not differ from a precedent in terms of limiting social media to social networks.
6. Using Internet and mobile technologies to transform communications into interactive dialogue".

This definition of social media is limited to modern technological media.

Through the advanced definitions of the concept of social media, the researcher made the following observations:

The general features and commonalities of the advanced definitions are as follows:

1. Its participation in referring to the segment targeted by social media, namely the members of society.
2. Its agreement to consider interaction as a mainstay in social media.
3. The trend of the majority of definitions towards limiting the concept of social media to the circle of social networking sites, and the rest of the electronic forms of communication such as blogs, forums, etc.
4. Some definitions tend to define the concept of social media through the general goals that should be achieved.

Reasons for the difference in defining the concept of social media:

The researcher estimates that the reason for the difference in defining the concept of social media is due to the following reasons:

1. The lack of writings on social media compared to some other types of media, such as political and security media, for example.
2. The emergence of social networks, where a large segment of people became acquainted with launching the concept of social media on these networks, considering that they provided the community members with a space to express their opinions, raise their problems, and raise their issues; In addition to providing the opportunity to communicate with each other more than before; Which contributed greatly to the proportion of this type of media to society.
3. The broadness of the meaning of the concept of community; Where it is called the various human groups.
4. Differing ideas, concepts, starting points and orientations of researchers, which is the matter in determining the totality of human science concepts.
5. The great interdependence between a range of societal issues; Where all of these issues, such as political, economic, cultural, etc., overlap in terms of causes and results.

Through the foregoing definitions about the concept of social media, and in light of the observations made by the research about those definitions, social media can be defined as “the media directed from the community to the community itself with the intention of achieving a purpose”. So; Social media is a type of media, directed to any society, and it has its goals and objectives that it seeks to achieve through its various available means and tools.

The relationship between social media and other sciences:

There is a strong relationship between this type of media and some other sciences. If we look closely at the reality of social media, we will find that other sciences intertwine and overlap with it, and we may try to clarify this relationship through what is to come.

Psychology can be considered as one of the most important sciences affecting social media, as it revolves in its entirety about human behavior, and its theories and parts can be employed to communicate information, ideas and news in a manner consistent with what leads the human mind to be affected and convinced of it.

To confirm the strength of this relationship, we find, for example, that dozens of psychologists choose programs with great care, and carefully prepare them to serve US policy in the Arab region.

Another influential science in social media is linguistics; Where this science is no less than other sciences in terms of directly affecting it, as it relates to one of the most important pillars of the media process, which is the message's utterance and its moral connotations. Man is often affected by the words, expressions and contexts in the content of social media, which often affects his interaction and response, as well as the formulation of his awareness and identification of his intellectual identity.

For example: The term “spiritual refreshments” in some social media sometimes refers to alcohol, which is contrary to the reality of the thing on the one hand, as it is not refreshing, and it is not a real name for the thing on the other hand, as the receiver may delude through this word that it is permissible, or perhaps His benefit is when he is ignorant of it, and he may be affected by this wording even if he is aware of its truth. As this may inherit several things such as familiarity or palatability, especially if this is repeated and spread and circulated on several satellite channels or in the writings of a number of writers, bloggers and famous social media, especially if they are of a specific nationality or nationalities, and the communities of these genera are classified as committed societies Religious and socially conservative.

The matter becomes clearer when some other words, such as: (emotional relations) are used to refer to (forbidden relationships), and it is similar to the use of the term (homosexuals) to (homosexuals), or the expression of (the dead man) with (the martyr) in order to provoke sympathy and interaction, and to replace (Divorce) with (separation) to avoid expressing words and terms associated with religion and replace them with legal terms or imported from other cultures. In fact, it is reported that many of the concepts and common words in some social media carry with it meanings and connotations that may be abhorred by the recipient by nature, but they are passed to him through twisted concepts and contexts to become entrenched in his awareness as presented.

The second topic: means, tools, types and characteristics of social media

Since social media is a type of media and a branch of it, it is obvious that it shares with it in terms of means and tools, which we will highlight in the following lines, as social media vary between visual, audio, written, read and printed, as follows:

1. The book: It is one of the most prominent social media, through which it is possible to address the community and address its problems and issues in order to make an impact on it, such as guidance, education, and guidance; Rather, it can be considered the most important, oldest and most established social media, due to the possibility of keeping it for re-reading with the possibility of circulation, lending and reference at any time. Therefore, circulation is one of the most prominent features of the book, in addition to its continued spread and occupation of its place in particular, despite the development and diversity of other means, In addition to the possibility of addressing long issues that need research and detail. Perhaps one of its main drawbacks is that it is easily damaged, lost, or confiscated.
2. The sermon: It is one of the oldest media arts, as people relied on it in the past to communicate information and ideas among themselves, and it is the mother of mass media with influence and enthusiasm, and every sermon carries an idea or meaning, whether social or political..etc, which in turn contributes to the process of different media.
3. The lecture: It is also one of the ancient media arts and is related to science and study more closely than other media purposes. At first glance, it seems that there is a great similarity between the sermon and the lecture. However, the lecture is distinguished by its reliance on abstract facts, accurate statistics, and logical arguments, without relying on influencing emotions, in addition to the possibility of using it in various scientific fields and human knowledge; Compared to the limited areas of use of the sermon; Which is often confined to the political and religious sphere.
4. The Internet: It is an electronic network that connects millions of computers and mobile phones in the world to each other, and for this reason it was called the World Wide Web. This network feeds many companies, individuals and institutions with all kinds of information in various fields, and its most prominent features are: crossing political borders, It is censored to some extent. While it is distinguished by some characteristics such as the multimedia that the receiver uses for multiple senses depending on the displayed content of sounds and images, overlapping together in a single message.
5. The Press: The press is one of the relatively old social media. It preceded cinema, radio and television by more than two hundred and fifty years. It is one of the most important and wide-ranging means, and it has the most effective impact on the awareness and conscience of the recipients.
6. Television: It can be considered one of the most successful social media for its ability to address and influence society, due to its combination of the three influential elements: sound, image and movement. Television also represents an effective educational, educational, and entertainment tool if it is well used and directed, especially in the current era after The multiplicity of its channels and the diversity of its contents.
7. progesterone A: Radio transmission is also considered one of the most efficient social media, due to its speed and ability to spread rapidly, and it can address a large segment of audiences through the sense of hearing, which does not require much effort compared to some other media that need capabilities and efforts to deal and interact. with her.
8. Houses of worship: It can be considered one of the most important effective media in society. As it addresses a large segment of society in order to guide and guide them, especially in the educational, social and religious aspects.
9. Theatre: the father of direct visual and interactive arts, whether educational or entertainment, where it is possible through skits and other theatrical events to convey many messages that deal with community issues to directly influence its members.
10. Cinema: It is one of the means that has a great impact on the ideas and convictions of members of society, and seeks to influence the recipients towards certain situations or issues, and is often used as a means of entertainment, provided that this entertainment is also not without a reference, or a hint of certain glosses and goals. .

However, these means may vary in type and quantity from one society to another. Extremist and remote societies, such as the Bedouin society or the countryside, may not have some social media such as theater and cinema, compared to central societies such as the city, whose residents and patrons enjoy, in most cases, each according to his ability and capabilities, in general. Social media.

Types of social media and its characteristics Social media varies in terms of its impact on individuals and groups into two types:

The first type: the general social media, which is the media directed to all of society, with all its segments and categories, without focusing on a particular segment or category.

The origin of this type is that it has an equal level of impact on all members of society, but it may vary in terms of interest by individuals or community segments, as some may be interested in it and others ignore it. And it does not attract others who are interested in sports. In any case, the discourse in this type of media is directed to all individuals and members of society.

The second type: Specialized social media, which is the media whose organizers aim to deliver a media message to a specific group or segment of society. That is, this type is directed towards a specific category or segment; Such as students, women or the disabled.

The bottom line here: that social media may be directed to the general community, or it may be limited to targeting a specific group or segment.

Social media features:

It is well known that the uniqueness of something and its distinction from others is only by the presence of something that distinguishes it, for the individualization of social media from other types of media was only for characteristics that

distinguished it from the rest of the media types, and in the light of all the foregoing about the concept of social media, we can extract its most prominent characteristics as follows: next one:

1. The first characteristic of social media is that it is based on presenting its content to societies and not to individuals; In the sense that this type of media is not concerned with individual issues or problems, the focus is on groups or societies in general.
2. The discourse in this type of media is originally to be collective, addressing and addressing a human group or society, meaning that social media, although it is numerous, diversified and branched, yet shares the collective discourse method.
3. Social media aims to influence collective behavior, not individual, in the sense that it aims to change, direct or inform at the collective level, unlike personal media that seeks to influence the individual and personal level.
4. Comprehensiveness, which means that social media targets all kinds of societies, whether small or large, whether they are organizations, bodies, institutions, etc.

Conclusion

The current study reached a number of results, which are:

1. Definitions of the concept of social media fluctuate between limiting it to the generality of what is provided by electronic social media, and the generality of what is issued by the media in a society.
2. There are many legal controls and provisions that should be observed and adhered to in the means, messages and topics of social media by including them in binding legal articles regulating media work.
3. The rapid development and tremendous progress in the means and tools of the media have increased the interest of the international legislator in the situation and rights of journalists in all aspects surrounding their work.
4. The numerous international conventions and recommendations are evidence and presumption of the international legislator's interest in the category of journalists and media work, and there is a remarkable success in unifying the professional work rules for journalists and media professionals, which were able to include protection and immunity for the journalist and succeeded in keeping pace with him in all stages of his work, starting from receiving information until disseminating it to public opinion. And her success in moving it.

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() "The Internet sites that users can participate in and contribute to creating or adding to their pages easily." Or they are: "The websites in which the Internet provides services to its users that allow them to create a personal page displayed to the public within a specific site or system, and provides a means of communication with acquaintances the page creator, or with other users of that website or online system.

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